

THE ROLE OF TRINITY OF PERSUASION BY ARISTOTLE IN PUBLIC SPEAKING CLASSES

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the techniques related to the theory of parts of persuasion developed by the scientist and philosopher Aristotle.

Key words: ethos, pathos, logos, emotion, intelligence, logic, moral.

It is well known that one of the most crucial aspects of language learning that students should focus on is public speaking. There will be a lot of misconceptions in the speech process if a student picks up a language, thoroughly studies each theory, but then makes blunders in the communication process—especially while speaking in front of others. Speech and language are highly significant and interconnected activities; effectively using language and expressing the message in a single manner is crucial for both the speaker and the listener. The rationale is that various forms of cross-cultural communication take place via a single language. Better or worse relations between countries may result from this. It is simple to determine a person's position in society by appropriate speech use, situation-based speech selection (tone, pace, and style), and purposeful conversational organization.

The method developed by the renowned scientist and philosopher Aristotle is highly helpful in this regard. For generations English-speaking people, particularly those who speak in public, have been captivated by this seemingly complex yet incredibly useful theory. That is to say, it is much simpler to select one and deliver a meaningful speech based on the circumstances.

The Greek philosopher Aristotle (384-322 b.c.e.) classified properties of items and concepts in the known universe. One of his most fundamental discoveries was the composition of persuasive speaking. Although Aristotle identified the “three appeals” that make it up 23 centuries ago, when the known universe was smaller, they are timeless. Persuaders of all types have been relying on them since, including we who appeal to users through UX design.

The Trinity of Persuasion. Looking at any act where a speaker tries convincing another person or group, we might first see someone arguing a point. From debating in school to selling merchandise on TV, persuaders state a case to win over an audience in order for the latter to do something. The persuader needs a) an objective, b) an audience, and c) to reach that audience with a message. Specifically, he/she has to persuade them, as opposed to an authority figure ordering them to do something. Aristotle identified that the art of persuasion consisted of three parts:

- 1) **Logos** — Appealing to Logic;
- 2) **Pathos** — Appealing to Emotions;
- 3) **Ethos** — Appealing to Ethics, Morals and Character.

Aristotle proposed three means of persuasion because he claims that the speech consists of three things; the speaker, the subject addressed in the speech and the hearer. The three means of persuasion can be found either in the character of the speaker (ethos) or in the

argument of the speech (logos) or in the emotional state of the hearer (pathos) was developed and designed based on a comprehensive literature review of rhetoric to be used in analyzing the three appeals of persuasion. [2;116]

In the case of **logos**, a persuader uses facts, statistics, quotations from reputable sources/experts, as well as existing knowledge. This is the side of the argument that can prove how solid it is based on facts alone.

Pathos involves delivering the argument in a way that appeals to the audience's emotions. Logos alone has facts that are cold, flat and 'dead'. For example, a scientist speaking at a world convention can talk about global warming and bring up facts and figures about how many tons of ice melt into the sea every year. There, she would be using logos. However, by arguing about the impact of global warming on living things, for instance, how many polar bears will die if the current trend continues, she'll tap the emotions of the audience. Pathos is the emotional vehicle that carries the logos to the audience.

Ethos has to do with who the persuader is. His/her identity will have a great impact on how the audience takes the message. If our scientist had been running late, and a politician stumbled onto the stage and tried speaking for her, no one would take him seriously. He isn't a specialist in the field. Not only that, his general knowledge (and political agendas: he may want to distort facts about the topic for his own gain!) about global warming would fail to convince them of his "expertise". [1]

Our credibility is evident in three main ways:

1. **The quality of the message.** We need to ensure that our message is 'worthy of belief' (Aristotle): recognizes the audience's needs and motivations; contains all the necessary facts; is meaningful, clear, logical; avoids careless mistakes; is honest and ethical.
2. **The audience's perception of us as a communicator.** We need to make our 'own character look right' (Aristotle): project confidence; dress appropriately; know the subject; be well prepared; build rapport with the audience.
3. **Our reputation as a communicator independent from the message.** This can be shown by referring to appropriate sources of credibility such as rank, goodwill, expertise, image, or common ground. [3;2]

In summary, it is possible to demonstrate leadership and discover one's place in the team by giving a speech; however, one must use the appropriate persuasion technique depending on the context. Such excellent techniques will undoubtedly grant us ownership of a speech that is both lovely and significant.

References:

1. A Proposed Framework for Analyzing Aristotle's Three Modes of Persuasion Dr. Abdulrahman Alkhirbash (p.116)
2. Aristotle's three modes of persuasion Mike Baker, Aalto University School of Business (p.2-3)
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